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CONTACTS

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Website: <https://ist-journal.uz>

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DEVELOPMENT OF A LOGICAL-LINGUISTIC MODEL OF THE KOREAN NOUN CATEGORY AND CREATION OF A PREFIX AND AFFIX DATABASE

Yendirboyeva Zumrad Zohidjon qizi

Researcher at National University of Uzbekistan named after Mirzo Ulugbek

Email: yendirbayeva.zumrad1999@gmail.com

Abstract: This article examines the development of a logical-linguistic model of the noun category in the Korean language and the creation of an electronic database of prefixes and affixes attached to nouns. The study systematically analyzes the morphological, syntactic, and semantic features of Korean nouns and highlights their application in computational linguistics and machine translation systems. In addition, the prefixes and affixes involved in noun formation are classified. As a result, semantic databases have been developed that enable the optimization of processes such as automatic analysis, indexing, and translation of Korean nouns.

Keywords: Korean language, noun part of speech, logical model, linguistic model, semantic base, SSM metric, prefix, affix, suffix, corpus linguistics, machine translation, computational linguistics.

Annotatsiya: Mazkur maqolada koreys tilidagi ot soʻz turkumining mantiqiy-lingvistik modelini ishlab chiqish hamda otlarga qoʻshiluvchi prefiks va affikslarning elektron bazasini yaratish masalalari tadqiq etilgan. Tadqiqotda koreys tilidagi otlarning morfologik, sintaktik va semantik xususiyatlari tizimli ravishda tahlil qilinib, ularning kompyuter lingvistikasi va mashina tarjimai tizimlarida qoʻllanilishi yoritilgan. Shuningdek, otlarning hosil boʻlishida ishtirok etuvchi prefikslar va affikslar tasniflangan. Natijada koreys tilidagi otlarni avtomatik tahlil qilish, indekslash va tarjima qilish jarayonlarini optimallashtirish imkonini beruvchi semantik bazalar ishlab chiqilgan.

Kalit soʻzlar: koreys tili, ot soʻz turkumi, mantiqiy model, lingvistik model, semantik baza, SSM metrikasi, prefiks, affiks, qoʻshimcha, korpus lingvistikasi, mashina tarjimai, kompyuter lingvistikasi.

Аннотация: В данной статье рассматриваются вопросы разработки логико-лингвистической модели именной категории корейского языка и создания электронной базы данных префиксов и аффиксов, присоединяемых к именам существительным. В исследовании систематически анализируются морфологические, синтаксические и семантические особенности корейских существительных, а также освещается их применение в системах компьютерной лингвистики и машинного перевода. Кроме того, проводится классификация префиксов и аффиксов, участвующих в словообразовании существительных. В результате разработаны семантические базы данных, позволяющие оптимизировать процессы автоматического анализа, индексирования и перевода корейских существительных.

Ключевые слова: корейский язык, часть речи — существительное, логическая модель, лингвистическая модель, семантическая база, метрика SSM, префикс, аффикс, суффикс, корпусная лингвистика, машинный перевод, компьютерная лингвистика.

INTRODUCTION

In contemporary linguistics, the formal modeling of natural languages, the classification of linguistic units in the form of databases, and their integration into machine translation systems are considered among the most relevant areas of scientific research. In particular, the morphological structure of the Korean language, which belongs to the group of agglutinative languages, presents complex challenges in the process of computer-assisted language processing [1-3].

In the Korean language, nouns constitute one of the principal nominative units of a sentence and serve to denote objects, events, persons, and abstract concepts. Nouns can be expanded and new meanings can be generated through various grammatical markers, auxiliary affixes, and word-formation elements [4]. Therefore, developing a logical-linguistic model of Korean nouns and systematizing the prefixes and affixes attached to them within a unified framework is of significant theoretical and practical importance for machine translation and

natural language processing systems.

In recent years, numerous studies have been conducted on the development of electronic corpora, morphological analyzers, and automatic translation systems for the Korean language [5]. However, a comprehensive model integrating the logical-linguistic description of the noun category with a database of prefixes and affixes has not yet been sufficiently developed.

The aim of this study is to develop a logical-linguistic model of the noun category in the Korean language and to create an electronic database of prefixes and affixes used with Korean nouns.

The objectives of this study are as follows:

- to identify the linguistic characteristics of nouns in the Korean language;
- to develop a formal and logical model of Korean nouns;
- to classify noun-forming prefixes and affixes;
- to create a conceptual model of a database of prefixes and affixes;
- to adapt the developed model for use in computer-assisted translation and machine translation systems.

REVIEW OF LITERATURE ON THE SUBJECT

In studies on computational linguistics and machine translation systems, the works of Khakimov M.H. are of particular importance [1; 2].

The multilingual model-based computer translator technology proposed by Khakimov M.H. defines the theoretical foundations for formal modeling of natural languages and their integration into machine translation systems [1]. This approach addresses the representation of linguistic units in a structural and formal form and their transformation into a format suitable for algorithmic processing. This serves as one of the theoretical foundations of the $\mathbf{N = \{R, P, A, S, C\}}$ model developed in this study.

Furthermore, the method of formalizing natural languages in an input-expanding language developed by Khakimov M.H. enables the transformation of linguistic data into a formal system, allowing their interpretation by computer systems and supporting automatic processing [2]. This approach is particularly important for morphological analysis and the modeling of affixal structures, and it is directly applicable to segmentation of Korean nouns and the creation of an affix database.

Overall, these studies strengthen the relationship between linguistic modeling and machine translation and provide a theoretical justification for the effectiveness of formal approaches in computational linguistics.

The theoretical foundations of the noun category in Korean linguistics have been comprehensively examined by Lee Ik-seop and Chae Wan, who described the grammatical and semantic characteristics of Korean nouns in detail [6]. In their studies on Korean grammar, Nam Ki-shim and Ko Young-geun provided a scientific explanation of the morphological structure of nouns [7].

The Korean language has also been analyzed from the perspective of computational linguistics in the studies of Kang Beom-mo and Kim Jin-woo, who focused on issues related to morphological analysis and corpus linguistics [8-9].

In Uzbek linguistics, the problems of modeling natural languages have been investigated by S. Muhamedov, A. Po'latov, and other scholars [14]. These studies addressed the formal representation of linguistic units and their integration into machine translation systems.

Although the grammatical characteristics of Korean nouns have been extensively studied in existing research, the development of a unified system that combines a logical-linguistic model of the noun category with a database of prefixes and affixes has not yet been sufficiently explored.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

In this study, a comprehensive approach was employed to develop a logical-linguistic model of the noun category in the Korean language and to create an electronic database of prefixes and affixes associated with Korean nouns. The research was based on the following methods:

- **Descriptive method** – used to describe the morphological and semantic characteristics of Korean nouns;
- **Structural analysis method** – used to identify the internal structure of nouns and the patterns governing their combination with affixes;
- **Componential analysis method** – used to analyze the semantic composition of nouns;
- **Formal modeling method** – used to represent linguistic units in the form of mathematical and logical models;
- **Database design method** – used to systematize prefixes and affixes in an electronic database.

The research materials consisted of academic grammars of the Korean language, the Korean National Corpus (Korean National Corpus), contemporary dictionaries, and relevant scientific publications [10].

Korean nouns can be formally represented on the basis of the following model:

$$N = \{R, P, A, S, C\}[16]$$

Here:

N – noun;

R – root;

P – set of prefixes;

A – set of affixes;

S – semantic features;

C – grammatical markers.

According to this model, a noun is formed based on the following formula:

$$N = P + R + A$$

For example:

◆ 최고학생 (the best student)

◆ 최고 + 학생

◆ P + R

◆ 불행 (unhappiness)

◆ 불 + 행

◆ P + R

◆ 학자 (scientist)

◆ 학 + 자

◆ R + A

This model enables automatic segmentation and morphological analysis of Korean nouns.

The proposed database consists of the following fields (Table 1):

Table 1. Sample Entries from the Korean Noun Affix Database and Their Functions¹

ID	Affix	Type	Function	Example	Translation
001	불-	Prefix	Negation meaning	불행	misfortune
002	-자	Suffix	Person marker	학자	scholar
003	-성	Suffix	Property/quality	가능성	possibility
004	-감	Suffix	Feeling/sense	책임감	sense of responsibility

This database can later be integrated into machine translation systems in SQL or XML formats.

In the Korean language, true prefixes are relatively limited in number. They mainly serve to intensify meaning, express negation, or form new concepts (Table 2).

Table 2. Common Korean Noun-Forming Prefixes and Their Semantic Functions²

Prefix	Meaning	Example	Translation
불-	negation	불행	misfortune
무-	absence / lack	무의식	unconsciousness
비-	opposition / non-	비공식	unofficialness
반-	half / opposition	반정부	anti-government
초-	super / ultra	초고속	ultra-high speed
재-	re- / again	재건	reconstruction
친-	close / friendly	친환경	eco-friendliness
고-	high / classical	고전	classic
대-	large / great	대도시	metropolis
소-	small	소기업	small enterprise

Main noun-forming prefixes in Korean

These prefixes are most often combined with Sino-Korean noun bases [11].

In the Korean language, suffixes are one of the most productive means of noun formation (Table 3).

1 Source: Author's compilation.

2 Source: Author's compilation.

Table 3. Main noun-forming suffixes in Korean³

Suffix	Function	Example	Translation
-자	person marker	학자	scholar
-가	profession / expert	작가	writer
-인	person	한국인	Korean person
-성	quality / property	가능성	possibility
-력	ability / capacity	능력	ability
-감	feeling / sense	책임감	sense of responsibility
-화	process	산업화	industrialization
-론	theory	언어론	linguistics theory
-학	field of study	언어학	linguistics
-법	method / rule	문법	grammar
-관	building / institute	도서관	library
-실	room	연구실	laboratory
-국	organization	우체국	post office
-장	place	운동장	stadium
-품	product	식품	food product

Semantically, affixes can be classified into the following groups:

Person-denoting affixes:

-자, -가, -인

Abstract concept-forming affixes:

-성, -감, -력

Field of science / academic discipline affixes:

-학, -론

Institution and place-denoting affixes:

-관, -실, -장

Process-denoting affixes:

-화

This classification enables the grouping of affixes within a database system [15].

ANALYSIS AND RESULTS

During the study, the morphological and semantic features of Korean nouns were analyzed, and a formal and logical model representing these features was developed. This model made it possible to integrate the structural components of Korean nouns—root, prefix, suffix, grammatical markers, and semantic features—into a unified system.

The analysis showed that suffixation is the primary means of noun formation in the Korean language. Although prefixes are relatively limited in number, they play an important role in creating new meanings. In particular, prefixes such as 불-, 무-, and 비- are actively used to express negation or oppositional meanings [12].

As a result of the study, a conceptual model for an electronic database of prefixes and suffixes used with Korean nouns was developed. This model enables the storage of information about affixes, including:

- phonetic form;
- grammatical type;
- semantic function;
- usage frequency;
- examples;
- translation equivalents.

The created database has the following advantages:

1. It can be used in the development of morphological analyzers.

3 Source: Author's compilation.

2. It enables accurate analysis of nouns in machine translation systems.
3. It contributes to enriching Korean–Uzbek electronic dictionaries.
4. It serves as a linguistic resource for Natural Language Processing (NLP) systems.[15]
5. It can be applied in corpus linguistics research.

Since Korean is an agglutinative language, morphological analysis plays a crucial role in the machine translation process [13]. Identifying the structural components of nouns directly affects translation quality.

For example:

가능성

가능 + 성

(imkon + lik) → possibility

책임감

책임 + 감

(responsibility + feeling) → sense of responsibility

연구자

연구 + 자

(research + person) → researcher

Using the proposed model, these units can be automatically segmented and semantically analyzed.

CONCLUSIONS AND SUGGESTIONS

In this study, a logical-linguistic model of the noun category in the Korean language was developed, and a conceptual solution for creating an electronic database of prefixes and suffixes attached to nouns was proposed.

Based on the results of the study, the following scientific conclusions were drawn:

1. Korean nouns represent a complex system consisting, from a morphological perspective, of roots, prefixes, and suffixes.
2. In noun formation, suffixes are the most productive means, while prefixes serve to modify meaning.
3. The proposed model $N = \{R, P, A, S, C\}$ enables a formal description of nouns.
4. The electronic database of prefixes and suffixes optimizes the processes of automatic processing of the Korean language.
5. The research results serve as a theoretical and practical foundation for developing Korean–Uzbek machine translation systems.

In the future, it is planned to further improve the mathematical models of the noun category and evaluate them using the SSM metric, as well as to create a comprehensive linguistic database covering all grammatical affixes in the Korean language.

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